

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND NEW TENDENCIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This article discusses the importance of identifying and distinguishing innovative approaches and new tendencies in modern education. It highlights the need for educators to stay current with emerging trends and technologies in order to provide students with a relevant and effective learning experience. The article also emphasizes the role of creativity, flexibility, and adaptability in implementing these new approaches to enhance student engagement and achievement. Furthermore, it underscores the significance of research and collaboration in developing and sharing best practices in modern education.

Key words: Innovative approaches, new tendencies, Education trends, student engagement, creative teaching methods, adaptability in education, research in education, collaboration in education.

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It is known that the organizational form of the educational process in higher educational institutions consists of lectures, seminars, practical exercises, laboratory work, independent work of students and various practices. Any organizational form defines an educational model that includes educational goals, content, and other elements. The organizational form of education reveals the essence of the educational model. The quality of the educational process is ensured by factors such as educational standards, educational programs, the scientific potential of professors and teachers involved in the educational process, the potential of learners, technical tools of the educational process, educational technologies, and the quality level of educational process management. The world experience shows that the widespread penetration of information and communication technologies and the Internet into the field of education also paves the way for the globalization of educational services.

Innovative approaches in modern education refer to novel and creative methods, strategies, or technologies that are used to enhance teaching and learning experiences. These approaches often involve thinking outside the box and breaking away from traditional educational practices to improve student engagement, motivation, and outcomes.

On the other hand, new tendencies in modern education refer to emerging trends or patterns that are gaining popularity and shaping the future of education. These tendencies may include shifts in curriculum design, changes in assessment practices, advancements in educational technology, or evolving pedagogical philosophies.

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While innovative approaches focus on the implementation of cutting-edge ideas and practices, new tendencies highlight broader shifts and developments within the education sector. Both are essential for driving progress and improvement in education by fostering creativity, adaptability, and responsiveness to the changing needs of students and society.

Such a symmetrical connection between the educational model and the organizational form helps the professor-teacher to distinguish many trends in his professional environment and to choose correctly how to organize the educational process in his work. In the current modern education process, many examples can be given that show such a connection between the educational model and the organizational form. For example, the rapid development of open distance education has created new forms of organization not found in other educational models, including virtual, synchronous videoconferencing.

However, no matter how the name of the constituent elements of organizational forms of higher education takes a new form, the main elements are lectures, practical training, laboratory work, seminars, independent work and practices, and among them, lectures play an important role in students' acquisition of theoretical knowledge, formation of practical skills and qualifications. According to the National Program, information provision of the educational process will develop on the basis of modern information technologies and computer networks.

The publishing base of science and education will develop. Educational, teaching-methodical, scientific innovative, modern technologies are perfected and applied to the educational process. The teacher looks for the ways, methods and methods, teaching forms, methods and tasks that activate the students and are convenient for him and the learner. By teaching students to think independently, it increases the high quality and efficiency of the educational process.

Ensuring a high-quality indicator of the implementation of the national program, improving the educational content based on the State educational standards. Monitoring works are being carried out at the school, district, city, republic level to determine whether the knowledge acquired by students meets these standards by applying the State educational standards in the educational process in all academic subjects. The teacher looks for the ways, methods and methods, teaching forms, methods and tasks that activate the students and are convenient for him and the learner. Therefore, pedagogical technology, didactic technology, educational technology are considered the most effective tools in the educational process. They are widely used in world pedagogical practice

In teaching technology, the student will have a clear idea of the event and event by live observation of the event and event. The teacher summarizes his ideas, and as a result, students have a clear understanding of this or that problem.

Studying each incident in the lesson in interaction, together, provides them with dialectical understanding. After all, dialectical thinking is the most reliable way to know reality, and it allows to synthesize the accumulated knowledge in each subject based on the dialectical method.

Integrative study of educational material in the lesson is an important pedagogical process, which is carried out depending on the nature of the topic and the set goal. When studying topics based on integrative technologies, students gain a

broader knowledge than they have in a single subject. Otherwise, it will negatively affect the quality of knowledge and the general development of students' worldview, as well as the teacher's work.

Summary: In summary, innovative approaches in modern education involve creative and novel methods, strategies, or technologies that enhance teaching and learning experiences by breaking away from traditional practices. These approaches focus on implementing cutting-edge ideas to improve student engagement and outcomes. On the other hand, new tendencies in modern education refer to emerging trends or patterns that shape the future of education, such as shifts in curriculum design, changes in assessment practices, advancements in technology, or evolving pedagogical philosophies. While innovative approaches emphasize the implementation of innovative practices, new tendencies highlight broader shifts and developments within the education sector, driving progress and improvement by responding to the changing needs of students and society.

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